

Stress Reduction and Management for Improved Mental Health Globally

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Abstract

Background: Stress is one of the leading public health challenges of the modern time. It is known to exacerbate and lead to long term negative health effects such as heart diseases and mental health disorders. The COVID-19 pandemic has also increased the levels of stress in patients as social support has decreased with isolation and quarantine processes during the time of the pandemic.

Objective: This paper will go on to discuss what measures can be taken to reduce stress for improved physical and mental health.

Method: For this project extensive literature review was conducted to determine what leads to stress and how intervention approaches can stop stress. Additionally, given the regency of the COVID-19 pandemic, this research specifically wanted to make recommendations that would most help people who felt the effects of social isolation due to the pandemic and make further recommendations based on this. This paper has utilized literature and data all from within the past ten years, utilizing the highest regarded sources, and subject matter expertise across authors to make recommendations and inferences.

Conclusion: This study has found that exercise such as yoga, deep breathing meditation, and having a positive attitude through personality traits such as playfulness, are all ways in which a person can reduce stress and improve their mental and physical health for improved quality of life and longevity. Lifestyle and a person's profession also heavily influences levels of stress. Students have been shown to have the most increased levels of stress during the pandemic as well as hospital workers due to the change of setting and uncertainty for students and the high stress of contracting COVID-19 and putting one's life on the line during the pandemic.

Introduction

Hans Selye is known as the father of modern stress. A pioneer in stress research is credited with coining the term stress. In 1936, he defined stress for the first time, describing it as the body's general reaction to any harmful substance. Similarly, in 1976, Lazarus defined stress as a situation in which someone cannot bear the pressure on them and reacts negatively [1]. Job stress is something that makes people feel depressed and frustrated and have mental breakdowns due to high pressure [1]

Around the world, university students frequently experience academic stress, which has a detrimental impact on their mental health [2,3]. Stress and sadness

are most prevalent among medical students [4]. The demands of college life, including frequent tests, deadlines, not managing time properly, postponed projects, a lousy overpopulated living place, working while studying, adjusting to a new environment or even a new country, the imbalance between academic and personal life, and numerous other personal issues, are the leading causes of academic stress.

Companies and organizations in France have also grappled with commonplace stress, with the Laboratoire Lescuyer survey in 2022 showing that up to 90% of the French population is stressed. This is incredibly unhelpful for students because it is their task to separate the signal from the noise. According to the

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National Institute of Statistics and Economic Analysis data, in 2020/2021, universities in France were attended by 1,650 782 students, 0.9% more than in the previous year, and the occupancy density reached 19.2%. First-year students increased by 1.7%, and the overall student body increased by 2.2% per year in the past five years, with almost 220000 new students each year. Despite this expansion, prevailing and evolving economic, social, and political reality remains a hurdle for students as they undergo stress due to performance demands, poverty, and future instability [5].

Hypertension is a global issue affecting over a billion, case of stress [6]. Overweight and obesity pose serious public health risks. They raise the chance of developing noncommunicable illnesses, including diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and several types of cancer, this paper examines the most recent research on the causes, effects, and treatments for overweight and obesity. To reverse the obesity epidemic and promote healthy eating and active living for everyone, the research calls for immediate action and a comprehensive strategy that promotes healthy eating and diet, increased physical exercise and modifications to environmental factors [7].

Background of the Study

Stress is a multifaceted phenomenon that has been studied in depth across many fields, most especially psychology. It was first introduced in APA reports in 1950 due to its importance in explaining emotional and physiological reactions. Many psychological terms are associated with stress, including anxiety, tension, emotional breakdown, and frustration. Stress also allows for the prescriptive examination of physiological effects stemming from psychological occurrences [8]. Stress is not invariant, and its meaning depends on life conditions. Cognitive restructuring is widely perceived as a process that includes assessing events, thoughts, feelings, and actions. Although some people consider stress a result of external environmental conditions, stress is a reaction to external environmental conditions by the person [8].

Coping strategies for stress are typically categorized into two types: There are further coping modes that include appraisal-based coping involving consultancy and search-based coping, which provides for escapist, delayers, replacers, and seekers.

The idea of stress was first defined in the middle of the seventeenth century by physicist Sir Robert Hooke as the ratio of the force causing deformation to the area to which the force is applied to a flexible material. In psychology and other disciplines, stress becomes a physical, mental, or cognitive adjustment to external events that upset an individual's equilibrium, which results in proactive behaviors to regain stability [9].

Stress is derived from a person's interaction with his environment or can be defined as an environmental

quality where excessive or inadequate stress is harmful. An optimal level of stress makes people work harder. In contrast, more-than-optimal and less-than-optimal levels cause anxiety, depression, sleep disorders, and marital strife, thus affecting health and efficiency at the workplace [9].

Stages of Stress

In 1999, Seaward described stress in four stages. Starting from the body to the brain, it sends sensory transmission. If no threat is detected, it means there is no stress. However, if a symptom is detected, the body enters the alert phase, and the hormone disbalance occurs until the threat disappears and the body returns to equilibrium. In 1976, Hans Selye outlined a sequence for the stress response, starting with the "alarm" phase, where the sympathetic nervous system prepares the body to handle the threat. If stress persists, the body enters the "resistance" phase, marked by fatigue. Prolonged stress leads to the "fatigue" and "normalization" stages, where proper strategies are needed to recover [10].

The stress response unfolds in three stages:

Figure 1: Various Stages of Stress

Source: [10]

Alarm Stage: The 1st stage is the alarm stage, in which the body reacts to a stressor. The brain sends signals to our nerve, which sends adrenaline to give out the 'fight or flight' signal. The visible sympathetic reactions include a rise in heart rate, raised blood pressure, ways of respiration, and availability of oxygen to muscles and brain. Some other symptoms include procrastination in the digestion process, improvement in vision, frequent perspiring, and a tendency to drool less than usual.

Resistance Stage: If the stressor stays, the body fights the stressor in the resistance stage. Stress at this phase escalates; people get easily irritated, exhausted, and unable to deal with issues, negatively affecting them. Stress hampers the body also physically. Our body remains sick, like pain in the neck, shoulder, or head, due to the constant stress that has set automatically as

an alarm in our mind. If the stressor is finally overcome, the body returns to normal.

Exhaustion Stage: Stress can reach the third stage, exhaustion. The body drains all its energy after weeks, months, or even years of stress. The body and mind are exhausted; if no measures are taken to arrest the problem, the person will have no energy.

Stress Management for School Students

Characteristics of the academic environment can play a significant role in children’s mental health, such as the physical environment, the social climate, and the economic status of the school area [11], as we can see an increase in stress and mental disorders among students in recent times. As students spend most of their time in their institute, the educational institute is a favorable place to help them manage stress. Stress and mental health disturbance result from school-related challenges, which result in poor performance, dropout, and misbehavior [11]. Schools can see signs of mental health problems through academic or attendance decline. As studies say, effective school-based programs have been found to help reduce mental health deterioration issues and increase functional and academic functioning.

One of these effective interventions includes school-based stress management programs, a subset of interventions that target students and help them manage stress [13]. Such courses may consist of mindfulness exercises and relaxation training, and such courses may involve training in life skills and mostly contain cognitive behavior therapy. Evaluations of this program indicate that stress symptoms are lessened and coping enhanced, although some results are inconclusive, mixed, or minimal as implemented to specific student populations. Results say that these treatments are essential and, when delivered

effectively, can translate into actual improvements in students’ everyday functioning.

The findings from meta-analyses of programs for managing stress arranged by the schools are primarily positive, but there are also some cases [12]. Some reviews involve adolescents only or distinguish between certain kinds of interventions; others fail to cover the intricate spectrum of factors contributing to stress in children. They recommend that the intervention be as early as possible, especially for children who experience anxiety during a change of class, for example, from kindergarten to primary class. Thus, investigating the efficacy of stress management programs for students less than ten must be considered an adequate early intervention.

Stressors for Both Native and Foreign Students

Cross-sectional research was conducted as part of the WHO World Mental Health International College Student Initiative (WMH-ICS) survey. Two Dutch universities—the Universiteit van Amsterdam and the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, were the recruiting sites for this project. Students who (1) were 18 or 18+, (2) were enrolled in one of these two institutions’ undergraduate or graduate programs, and (3) provided digitally informed permission for study participation were eligible to participate. Convenience sampling was used to recruit participants between March 2018 and September 2019. People within the researcher’s grasp participate in the study using this non-probability sampling technique. Several methods were used to carry out the recruitment [14].

Except for health-related stress, overseas students reported far greater stress levels than domestic students. Figure 2 illustrates the differences in stressors between native and overseas pupils.

Figure 2: Mean Scores for Domestic and International Pupils in Each Stressor Individually
 Source: [14]

Academic-related stress and achievements

The examined study and other works also argue that academic-related stress negatively affects students’ performance. According to WHO’s 1996 report [16],

one of the conditions for learning is providing an environment that can assure their emotional integrity. According to the OECD survey of students in 2015, stress is connected with schoolwork, tests, homework,

science, mathematics, and reading performance. Most striking is the fact that students in the bottom twenty-five percentile performance levels report much higher levels of anxiety than students in the top twenty-five percentile. For instance, 63 percent of the low performers always feel pressured or stressed over exams, irrespective of study, while only 46 percent of high performers feel pressured [16].

The studies also made it known that the emotional status of the students is associated with learning involvement. Positive emotions reflect better student engagement, while negative emotions result in low engagement, which impacts the student’s academic performance. According to Reschly, stress is the primary cause influencing student performance levels. Several research papers have been done on medical students, which show that students with higher stress

show lower performance in their studies. Overall, academic-related stress is a crucial activity pressure that affects students’ academic performance, and, as a rule, increased stress leads to poor performance [15].

Academic Stress Dimension

The current study was basic/substantive and founded on the deductive technique. Due to its nature and the necessity to link variables (time management and academic stress), a correlational level was used.

2200 students from a state university comprised the population—a sample based on factors consisting of 328 students from the specified university. The survey was employed as a method for gathering data. Therefore, two questionnaires were used: 1) "time management," which had 34 items, and 2) "academic stress", which had 30 items [17].

Figure 3: Variable Academic & Stress Dimension
Source: [18]

Figure 3, which presents a descriptive study of academic stress and its corresponding dimensions, shows that 16.8% of the students polled thought it was high, 67.7% thought it was ordinary, and 15.5% thought it was low. Just 16.5% thought the stress dimension was low, compared to 18.9% who thought it was high and 64.6% who thought it was average. 23.2% of respondents rated the symptoms dimension as high, 62.5% as ordinary, and 14.3% as low. Last but not least, of the total respondents, 19.2% thought the coping dimension was high, 61.0% thought it was expected, and 19.8% thought it was low [18].

Practice of Stress Management Behavior on Students

The research on stress management was done from November 2018 to July 2019; the research was carried out at Mekelle University Colleges in Mekelle, Tigray, Ethiopia. It is a public school of higher education. Situated 783 km from the capital of Ethiopia in Mekelle, Tigray [19].

Sixty-three research participants participated in a cross-sectional study. The research excluded unwell students (unable to attend class because of illness) who were engaged in fieldwork or withdrew.

Table 1: Undergraduate Student Stress Management Practice, 2019 (n = 633)

Item	Never	Sometimes	Often	Routinely
Focusing on identifying the emotional changes going on with us	254(40.1)	190(30)	126(19.91)	63(9.95)
Make proper responses to irrational issues	206(32.54)	218(34.44)	148(23.38)	61(9.64)
Positive and peaceful feelings about myself	212(33.5)	200(31.6)	174(27.49)	47(7.4)
Focusing on the reason for the stress to solve it	170(26.86)	238(37.6)	169(26.7)	56(8.85)

Make a queue of the work from more to less priority-based	269(42.5)	206(32.5)	140(22.1)	18(2.84)
At least 6–8hr sleep every night	152(24)	217(34.28)	196(30.97)	68(10.74)
Do muscle relaxation regularly	192(30.3)	315(49.77)	63(9.95)	63(9.95)
Concentrate on positive thoughts before sleeping	117(18.2)	302(47.71)	126(19.91)	28(4.4)

Source: [19]

Only 49.8% of students tried to invest some time regularly in relaxing muscles occasionally. Meanwhile, 28 subjects (4.4%) reported their ability to concentrate on positive emotions all night [19].

Further, the analysis indicated that most students rarely attempted to determine the origin of their stress, with only 169 students (26.7%) reporting doing so reasonably frequently. Only 9.9% of the students in the second part of the survey attempted to measure these changes, and 40.1% of learners did not even try. Also, 42.5% of students responded that they had never made schedules or prioritized in the past [19].

As for the sleeping schedule, only 68 students (10.7%) sleep 6-8 hours a night. Moreover, the greater significance is that 34.4% of students sometimes

responded appropriately to unfair problems, as indicated in Table 1 [19].

Stress System Framework

Numerous researchers have observed that stress comprises several components: stressor, stress response, and stressful stimuli. Stimuli, receptors, and cascades should all be included since the way stress affects the body is essentially the same as other signal transduction processes. Thus, we propose that the five fundamental components of the stress system framework should be stress, stressor, stress, stress response, and stress consequence Figure 4. This idea states that the stressful stimulus is the starting point, the outcome is the terminus, and the stressor, stress, and stress response are cascades [21].

Figure 4: Framework of Stress System Evaluation Over Time

Source: [21]

For instance, this framework assists in clarifying the facets of the stress system by working through oxidative pressure. Therefore, the stressors are reactive oxygen species (ROS), the stimuli that induce ROS are the stressful stimuli, the harm done by ROS is oxidative stress, an organism’s effort to counteract it is the oxidative stress response, and the biological outcomes of this stress are the consequences of oxidative stress [22].

The COVID-19 Effects on Student's Stress Level

COVID-19 has changed people’s lives and affected their psychological and physical well-being, including university students [20]. Stress reports among college

students have increased, during COVID-19 and post-pandemic and there are many more psychological problems now [23]. Multiple risk factors that predisposed the participants to heightened perceived stress included longer durations of quarantine over 14 days, lack of supply provisions, cardiovascular and respiratory disease, perceived infection threat, infection, or loss of a dear one [24, 27].

Surveying a respondent base of 937 college students, it was evident that the lives of these individuals had, in one way or another, been affected by COVID-19. The analyses revealed that 38.5% of the participants had a family member who was impacted by the virus, 57.2%

of the participants had to self-isolate at their homes, and 72.8% had only moderate symptoms of the virus. As much as 45.3% reported postponement of their tests due to the pandemic, and 53.4% reported attending online classes. The increased pandemic strain on an individual’s health, or that of a first-degree relative,

significantly predicted their increased perceived stress levels based on their PSS-10 scores and their scores from the four domains of behavioral, cognitive, physical, and emotional strain ($r > 0.76$, $p = 0.001$, $n = 363$) [26].

Table 2: How COVID-19 Affects Student Stress Even More

Effect of COVID-19 Pandemic on university students	F	%
COVID-19 affected students both -ve & +ve		
• Yes	937	63.9
• No	530	36.1
Effects of the pandemic on students' or their relative's health		
Students have mild symptoms of the virus	708	72.8
• Self-quarantine for a while	842	57.4
• Quarantine in hospital due to excessive symptoms of the virus	74	7.6
• Admitted to ICU due to COVID-19 infection	46	4.7
• Death occurred to relatives coz they were infected with COVID	377	38.8
Effects on the education system		
• Institutes have to cancel or postpone the exam	664	45.3
• Online classes	783	53.4
• The exams were replaced with more assignments	282	30.2
Correlation between the following and the impact of COVID-19 on the health of students or their family members among those students whose lives were adversely impacted by the pandemic (T = 937)	R	P
Symptoms of mental stress-related	0.73	0.00*
Symptoms considering physical stress	0.78	0.00*
Traits related to behavioral stress	0.81	0.00*
Traits related to cognitive stress	0.80	0.00*
Total traits related to stress	0.91	0.00*
Total score of PSS	0.68	0.00

Source: [26]

Stress management technique

It is essential to deal with stress, especially in the student’s case, and there are different ways to control the stress level. The Canadian Clinic Community Health Centre recommends several methods:

Relaxation is a controlled process of conscious relaxation of the muscles, internal organs, articulations, emotions, and mind. It should become natural over time and reduce physical and mental stress in the long term [29].

Meditation: Mindfulness meditation lowers stress, anxiety, depression, and other negative feelings by requiring concentration on the present moment. Being fully present takes effort and time, but with daily practice, the areas of the brain responsible for happiness and relaxation are activated in opposition to everyday stressors such as time constraints and conflicts with others [29].

Third-Wave Treatments: Third-wave treatments emphasize promoting well-being holistically more than symptomatology reduction or removal. They integrate

behavioral, cognitive, and psychological concepts associated with acceptance, spirituality, mindfulness, CBT, and individual values. For an intervention to be classified as a third wave, it should concentrate on changing the person's connection to their ideas and feelings instead of changing the substance of their thoughts or lowering or removing their emotions [30].

Deep Breathing: When we are tense, we should focus on using our diaphragm, or the muscle, just below the lungs, instead of the chest. This is known as diaphragmatic breathing, as it relaxes and positively impacts the body and mind. Breathing is one of the ways we take oxygen into our body; shallow breathing hampers this process, mainly when it is caused by anxiety. Pranayama helps the oxygen supply to the body's organs, reduces stress, and helps the heart relax [29].

Interpersonal Treatments: Interpersonal treatment approaches focus on improving communication between young people and essential adults, such as parents or instructors [30].

Being mindful: Often called "being present," mindfulness is focused on the present situation instead of concentrating on the future or the past by acknowledging the here and now [28]. Being mindful of our physical surroundings, the environment, our food and drink, and the feelings of the sun or wind on our skin are all examples of being present [31].

Identifying Stress through Experience Sampling

A study using experience sampling to organize, evaluate, and describe the current status of the literature on work stress surveillance was conducted using a breadth-first review and the formal research approach of systematic mapping. Three hundred fifty-

eight publications published between 2010 and 2021 were categorized by contribution, research type, and emphasis. The resultant research landscape provides practitioners and scholars with a summary of the advantages and disadvantages of applying the experience sampling approach to stress detection [32]. The survey found the factors that mainly cause stress. The figure shows that as the x-axis increases, the stress level in the y-axis is triggered. Research is primarily focused on coping with everyday stress and improving existing circumstances, but mental issues and work-related stress are also significant sources of stress [32].

Figure 5: Triggering Factors that Cause Stress
Source: [32]

Strategies for Coping with Stress

Reducing and managing stress is a challenge, and according to past studies, measures tailored towards handling stress differ in the following ways [33, 34]: Students most often mention several stress reduction methods. The responses received were as follows: 68.5% (1,005 students) chose isolation as their primary coping mechanism, whereas 66.5% (913 students) chose excessive sleeping. Nonetheless, it may also be noted that these strategies are themselves in one way or another. This concurs with the general understanding that students shut themselves out of social activities during stressful conditions and prefer to sleep more than usual. However, there are better ways to manage stress, which we will discuss below.

Physiological Tactics

Modifying one's physiological condition through techniques like deep breathing or expressive movements meant to dissipate instead of internal emotional experience (e.g., staring at unruly students) were additional emotion management techniques that used lower stress. Teachers were able to keep an eye on their emotions and evaluate the effects of those emotions by taking deep breaths. Additionally, faculty members reported exercising often, taking regular

breaks from work, and looking for alternative stress-relieving therapies (such as massage therapy). In other populations (such as government personnel, school teachers, and general university staff), these physiologically orientated techniques often help lower stress, enhance psychological well-being and sleep quality, and ease physical symptoms [34].

Playfulness

A caregiver's degree of playfulness has personal implications for stress management. This paper agrees with Magnuson and Barnett (2013), who argue that playfulness is a boundary condition for the stress-coping process by affecting cognitive evaluation. Playfulness as a coping response influences how a stressor is perceived and felt. So, it can aid in changing the contorted perception of a stressful situation, increasing flexibility, decreasing perceived stress, and improving resilience. Additionally, individuals scoring higher in playfulness use more coping strategies identified as adaptive or engaging in nature than those with less playfulness. Still, they use similar coping strategies as individuals with less playfulness. Bundy (1993) discussed that increased playfulness improves coping ability during complex life events, evidenced by playfulness enhancing adults' ability to cope with

stress. These conclusions raise the possibility that playfulness may be a protective asset, allowing people to manage higher levels of stress, which might otherwise result in increased psychological strain [36].

Yoga

Yoga is a tradition or discipline that originated in the East more than two thousand years ago, with the primary aim being spiritual health and controlling instincts and feelings. According to this, it is possible to master one’s emotions and thoughts besides breath control (pranayama). With time, gestural patterns were combined with breath control and relaxation to enhance the range of motion, alleviate suffering, and moderate undesirable feelings. It is now considered effective in handling several facts, affecting the mind, heart, lungs, and even cancer, besides depression and anxiety complaints [37].

Yoga has become practiced worldwide in different styles, including relaxation exercises. Some practices are mainly dedicated to pranayama, while others are to physical postures. One vinyasa flow incorporates breath with an organized practice of asana that generates a flow or meditation. In 2017, Mr Patel listed eighteen yoga actions, although some were repetitive. They involve standing poses and inversions and end with relaxation, an integral part of yoga’s physical and mental health [37].

Mindfulness

Mindfulness, therefore, means emphasizing the present moment and noting and acknowledging the facts about the present experience. It embraces watching what goes on around you and feeling physical and mental states. When the present is recognized, people pay more attention to surrounding circumstances, such as the warmth of the sun or the process of eating or drinking.

Awareness is also involved in identifying and attending to thoughts that are otherwise continuously rehearsed or negative. These thoughts will further cause stress and may manifest physically as anxiety or tension headaches. Awareness focuses on the body and its experience, for example, experimenting with movements during walking or sensing the surface on which one walks.

Several scientific studies indicate that mindfulness is helpful for physical and psychological health and is effective in preventing depression recurrence if the patient undergoes cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT). However, some find it impossible to maintain awareness. At the same time, the outside world interjects its presence, and thus, people must find special occasions to be mindful of their breathing and body [37].

Figure 6: A Mediation Model that Shows the Direct and Indirect Relationships between Coping Characteristics, Playfulness, Perceived Helplessness, and Self-Efficacy

Source: [34].

Work-Related Stress on Nurses

The study was done in 2013 and was ethics-approved by two research organizations in South Africa. Confused with cultural heterogeneity, four hospitals in Gauteng were purposively recruited by randomly choosing 2 public and 2 privates. The unit managers recruited the

targeted nurses at these hospitals, and invitation packs included statements explaining the purpose of the research. The questionnaires and agreement were given to them. Each hospital consisted of 300, who were requested to complete the question-answer session within three weeks with reminders. The self-

administered questionnaires were enclosed in individually sealed envelopes, in secure sealed boxes that only the researcher could open.

According to multiple linear regression, each burnout component is most closely linked to staff difficulties contributing to work-related stress. Every model deviated considerably from zero ($p < 0.05$). Table 3 shows that the most significant variation in emotional

exhaustion (16%), personal achievement (10%), and depersonalization (13%) may be attributed to staff concerns. After controlling for age, sex, level of education, ethnicity, and hospital type (local vs private), the additional variance in emotional weariness, depersonalization, and personal accomplishment was explained [38].

Table 3: Employee Problems and Weariness

Variables	B	SE B	β	t-Statistic
Employee Issues and Emotional Exhaustion				
Managing Employee	0.29	0.04	0.30	7.42 *
Insufficient and Bad Equipment	0.12	0.04	0.12	3.04 *
R2 = 0.16, F (9, 856) = 17.70, $p < 0.05$. * $p < 0.05$				
Employee Problems and Depersonalization				
Employee Management	0.17	0.03	0.20	4.90 *
Stock Control	0.09	0.03	0.11	2.83 *
R2 = 0.13, F (9, 856) = 13.55, $p < 0.05$. * $p < 0.05$				
Employee Problems and Personal Accomplishments				
Sticking to the Hospital Budget	-0.19	0.03	-0.22	-5.44 *
Managing Employee	-0.14	0.04	-0.16	-3.80 *

Source: [38,41]

Case study on factors affecting stress, anxiety & depression

A study was conducted on the Kiraj population to understand the factors affecting their stress, anxiety, and depression. The research involved 920 participants. The 21 items from the DASS (Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale) [39] were used to evaluate the issues under study. For the data analysis, both single and multiple regressions were employed. Stata version 12 was also used for all statistical analyses at the significance level 0.05 [39].

Of the 950 participants, 920 (96.84%) expressed a willingness to continue working together. The distribution of demographic and other research factors is displayed in Table 4. The participants had a mean age of 35.76 (SD = 15.69). Of them, 304 (30.04%) were from a high-income group, 437 (47.5%) were married, 327 (35.54%) held a university degree or higher, and 458 (49.78%) were female. Additionally, 8.03% (range: 6.62–9.45) reported a history of mental issues, while 57.02% (range: 54.45–59.59) of participants had a life expectancy within the normal range [39].

Table 4: The Rates of Extreme Depression, Stress, and Anxiety were 4.79%, 15.13%, and 13.28%, Respectively. Meanwhile, the Rates of Anxiety, Mild Depression, and Stress were 33.73%, 13.38%, and 43.53%, Respectively

Variables	Frequency (%)	Variables	Frequency (%)
Insurance	cover	health service use	Yes
	Non-cover		No
Gender	Male	Physician visit	Yes
	Female		No
Family Size	1	depression	Moderate
	2		Severe
	3		No
	4		Moderate
	>=5		Severe
Education Qualification	<High School Diploma	Stress	No

	High School Diploma	306 (33.26)	anxiety	Moderate	400 (43.53%)
	Associate's degree	110 (11.96)		Severe	139 (15.13%)
	≥Bachelor's degree	327 (35.54)		No	487 (52.99%)
Marital status	Married	437 (47.5)	Economic status	Low	306 (33.26)
	Single	411 (44.67)		Middle	305 (33.15)
	Divorced - widowed	72 (7.83)		High	304 (33.04)
#Age (Yrs. old)		35.76 ± 15.69	#BMI (kg/M2)		25.23 ± 4.80

Source: [40,41]

Global COVID-19 Pandemic: Worldwide Prevalence and Correlates of Psychological Stress

This study examines perceived stress during COVID-19 and its socio-demographic correlates during the pandemic, using data from 1685 adults across 57 countries collected between April 8 and May 11, 2020. The Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10) revealed an average 19.08 score indicating moderate stress. Factors linked to higher stress included being female (higher by 3.03 points) and having a four-year degree (higher by 3.29 points), while adults aged 75+ have reduced stress levels. They have around -7.46 points. Positive lifestyle habits like rest, exercise/yoga, and meditation decrease stress. Changes in work expectations also contributed to reduced stress. Germany reported significantly lower stress levels than the global average [40].

Tobit regression analysis was used to assess the predictors of the PSS-10 total score, where demographic means and lifestyle factors were controlled for. The model accounted for a mere 4% of the measured variation (P < 0.05; R² = 0.04). Key findings highlighted perceived stress as equal in adults over 75 years and lower than those aged 18–75. Perceived stress was higher among women than men and those with some college education or a four-year degree. The level of stress was higher among doctorate holders and students as well. Furthermore, better personal care, improved personal care since COVID-19, and changes to work expectations because of the pandemic were linked positively with perceived stress. [40].

Table 5: Global Correlations between Subjective Stress during the COVID-19 Epidemic and Sociodemographic Factor

Demographics	Beta Coef	Std Error	95% CI		p-Value
Marital Status					
Separated	-1.46	1.87	-5.15	2.22	0.43
Divorced	-0.67	1.03	-2.08	1.95	0.95
Widowed	-2.75	3.89	-10.41	4.90	0.48
Partnered	0.46	0.82	-1.15	2.06	0.58
Single	0.41	0.72	-1.01	1.82	0.56
Other	0.29	1.43	-2.51	3.10	0.21
Age					
25–34	0.85	1.00	-1.10	2.90	0.39
35–44	-0.13	1.11	-2.32	2.06	0.91
45–54	-1.32	1.13	-3.54	0.89	0.24
55–64	-2.14	1.23	-4.54	0.27	0.08
65–74	-2.04	1.75	-5.48	1.40	0.25
75+	-7.13	3.65	-14.29	0.03	0.05
Gender					
Female	3.17	0.51	2.18	4.16	0.00
Other	1.19	2.76	-4.23	6.62	0.67
Education					
Two-year	3.18	2.02	-0.79	7.16	0.12
Four-year	3.28	1.58	0.18	6.38	0.04
Master’s	2.11	1.60	-1.03	5.26	0.18
Doctoral	2.74	1.62	-0.43	5.92	0.09

Some college/no degree	3.25	1.65	0.02	6.48	0.05
Professional Degree (JD/MD)	1.47	1.76	-1.98	4.92	0.40
Employment Status					
Employed part-time	-0.25	0.86	-1.93	1.43	0.77
Student	1.82	1.00	-0.15	3.79	0.07
Laid off due to COVID	1.97	2.09	-2.13	6.08	0.35
Retired	-0.95	2.78	-6.41	4.51	0.73
Unemployed	0.31	2.02	-3.65	4.27	0.87
Other	-0.91	1.42	-3.69	1.87	0.52

Source: [40,41]

Conclusion

This paper has shown that stress, particularly among students is harmful to their academic lives and needs to be dealt with in a productive and meaningful way. Students are at a greater risk for negative outcomes of high levels of stress due to their young age and stage of cognitive development. Implementation of productive ways to deal with stress as aforementioned in the paper such as promoting playfulness, yoga, deep breathing exercises are all ways that students can deal with stress. The COVID-19 pandemic has also exacerbated students social isolation leading to higher levels of stress among students. More actions should be taken by University officials and instructors to ensure that mental health resources and opportunities for self-care to promote improved mental health are available. This paper also demonstrates the further need for Universities to allocate further funding to mental health programs such as Psychiatrists for the student body and Mental health counsellors on campus. Similarly, in the workplace we are seeing burn out of older adults in high stress jobs. Similar strategies must be implemented to decrease stress in these people through promotion of stress-coping activities which will lead to overall improved mental health and positive physical health impacts on the working population. Overall, this article finds that stress is one of the key issues of the modern day which affects both mental and physical health. More efforts are need to promote stress-coping strategies as described in this article to improve mental and physical health for all.

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Declaration of Conflicting Interests

The authors confirm that they have no conflicts of interest that could influence the presentation of the research findings in this article.

Author Contributions

The idea for the study was collectively brainstormed by all the contributors. MSI was tasked with creating the research design. IC undertook the data collection, analysis, and drafting of the preliminary report. The editing and approval of the final version of the paper were tasks undertaken collectively by all the authors.

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